

FATIGUE LIFE ESTIMATION OF LAMINATED GRP MATERIALS

UNDER VARIOUS RANDOM LOAD PATTERNS

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Summary

Presented here is a investigation on the fatigue life estimation of woven glass fabric reinforced plastics under subjected to various random load patterns of superimposed sinusoidal waves, Gaussian narrow band and wide band waves and so on. Fatigue tests were conducted under variable amplitude loading by a electro-hydraulic fatigue testing machine with a specially designed device to simulate a random-stress history of the actual service conditions. Then a procedure for predicting the fatigue life was suggested and discussed.

Introduction

An essential problem in fatigue research is the prediction of the life time of engineering structures under the actual service conditions. Nevertheless, the study on this subject is so far lacking for GRP materials in comparison with the metallic materials [1][2]. Most of the conventional fatigue test on GRP has been conducted under the sinusoidal constant amplitude loading. Whilst, it is well-known that a majority of the important structures such as aircraft, ships and other vehicles are subjected to loading of a random nature during their operation. Thus, the investigation on the quantitative prediction of fatigue life under the various random load patterns is of vital importance for the task of practical structural design and the reliable utilization of this material.

From such a standpoint, in this paper a series of fatigue tests have been conducted on Glass/Polyester specimens under the various kinds of random waves which were generated to simulate the actual service conditions. Discussions are then made on a procedure for the prediction of the expected fatigue life of GRP specimen subjected to the load spectra such as superimposed sinusoidal wave, narrow band wave, wide band wave, etc.

Specimen Preparation and Testing Procedures

All the specimens were prepared from laminates produced by hand-lay-up procedures. The material consists of polyester resin as matrix and satin woven glass fabric as reinforcement. The composition of the material and glass fiber content of the specimen tested are provided in Table 1. Each laminate was cut in the direction parallel to the warp of glass fabric to

the dimension shown in Fig.1. The pieces were then kept for more than two days just before testing under constant conditions of 296 K and 65% humidity.

All the fatigue tests were conducted under axial cyclic loading by a electro-hydraulic fatigue testing machine. For the fatigue test under the superimposed sinusoidal wave, fourteen different kinds of waves were produced by a programmable function generator, in which the sinusoidal waves of 5, 10, 15 and 20Hz were superimposed respectively on the sinusoidal wave of 1Hz and the values of stress amplitude for each wave were changed variously as well. Simulation of the Gaussian random waves, narrow band and wide band was performed on a Mini-scale computer (PC-8001 MK-2) with the aid of a subroutine.

Table 1 Material of the specimen and its glass fiber content.

Matrix	Polyester resin(Polylyte FG-284)
Reinforcement	Satin woven glass cloth(SLS-212)
Glass content by volume	40 (%)

Fig.1 Fatigue test specimen.

Fig.2 Schematic figures of superimposed sinusoidal wave.

Result and Discussions

Fatigue Life Prediction under Superimposed Sinusoidal Wave

Fig. 2 is a schematic figure of superimposed sinusoidal wave. Applied Stress values of primary and secondary waves are denoted by σ_1 and σ_2 and the corresponding frequencies are f_1 and f_2 , respectively. σ_{pmax} signifies the maximum peak stress values of superimposed waves involved. In the present work the primary frequency is always 1Hz, while the four kinds of secondary frequencies, 5Hz, 10Hz, 15Hz and 20Hz are used for investigation. Fatigue tests were conducted under fourteen kinds of superimposed sinusoidal waves where the combinations of the primary and the secondary values with respect to both the stress amplitude and the frequency were changed variously, as shown in Fig. 3.

Stress ratio		Primary frequency f_1 (Hz)			
σ_1/σ_2	$R = \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}$	Secondary frequency f_2 (Hz)			
		5	10	15	20
5/1	0.167				
2/1	0.333				
1/1	0.500				
1/2	0.667				
1/5	0.833				

Fig.3 Various superimposed sinusoidal waves investigated.

Fig.4 Relation between R and log η .

Fatigue life estimation will now be discussed for the various superimposed waves. First, the stress ratio of primary wave and secondary wave is defined as

$$R = \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2} \quad (1)$$

The value of R ranges from 0 to 1 corresponding to the combinations of the primary stress and the secondary stress. The case of R=0 is for the sinusoidal wave of frequency f_1 and R=1 is for that of f_2 . As is well known, it is quite complicated but basically a important problem to consider how to evaluate the number of repeated cycles of the superimposed wave, because not only the stresses, but also the frequencies of the primary wave and the secondary wave variously differ from each other. Now, let us consider that the frequency of superimposed wave is characterized with the aid of a equivalent wave assumed, f_{eq} , which is determined in the following manner(see Fig.2-(b)). Next, a frequency ratio η is defined as follows.

$$\eta = \frac{f_{eq}}{f_1} \quad (2)$$

Assume here that the relation between stress ratio R and the logarithm of η is linear as illustrated in Fig. 4, then

$$\eta = \left(\frac{f_2}{f_1} \right)^R \quad (3)$$

From Eq.(2) and Eq.(3), the equivalent frequency f_{eq} for a given stress ratio R is represented as

$$f_{eq} = f_1 \left(\frac{f_2}{f_1} \right)^R \quad (4)$$

Eq.(4) becomes Eq.(5) in case of the present work since $f_1 = 1\text{Hz}$.

$$f_{eq} = f_2^R \quad (5)$$

Table 2 shows the values of f_{eq} obtained for the superimposed waves tested here. Since the periodic time of the superimposed waves in the present work is 1 sec. at any case, it will be required to treat the secondary wave of 1 sec. as one block. In such meaning, the reduced fatigue data which is the fatigue life divided by the frequency of each wave have to be used as a basic data for predicting the fatigue life under superimposed waves.

Table 2 Equivalent frequency for each superimposed sinusoidal wave.

Stress ratio		Secondary frequency f_2 (Hz)			
σ_1/σ_2	$R = \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}$	5	10	15	20
5/1	0.167	1.308	1.468	1.570	1.648
2/1	0.333				2.714
1/1	0.500	2.236	3.162	3.873	4.472
1/2	0.667				7.368
1/5	0.833	3.824	6.813	9.552	12.139

Fig.5 S-N diagrams for the various frequencies.

Fig. 5 is the S-N diagrams for the various frequencies, in which the fatigue data were modified in the above-mentioned way. From these results, constants, m and $\log C$ of S-N relationship ($\sigma^m \cdot N_f = C$) are represented as a function of frequency.

$$m = 0.93f + 9.71 \quad (6)$$

$$\log C = 1.73f + 25.6 \quad (7)$$

It was suggested above that σ_{pmax} and f_{eq} should be used respectively for the evaluation of stress and frequency of the equivalent wave assumed in predicting the fatigue life under the superimposed wave. Thus, the prediction of the fatigue life, N_f under the superimposed sinusoidal waves can be made by the following equation.

$$\sigma_{pmax}^{0.93 f_2^{R+9.71}} \cdot N_f = 10^{1.73 f_2^{R+25.6}} \quad (8)$$

Figs 6 through Fig 9 are the comparisons between fatigue data under superimposed sinusoidal wave and the predicted fatigue lives for the various conditions of R , f_1 and f_2 . The values of fatigue life predicted by Eq. (8) are in excellent agreement with the test data for every case investigated.

Fig.6 Estimation of fatiguelife under superimposed sinusoidal wave ($f_1=1\text{Hz}, f_2=5\text{Hz}$).

Fig.7 Estimation of fatigue life under superimposed sinusoidal wave ($f_1=1\text{Hz}, f_2=10\text{Hz}$).

Fig.8 Estimation of fatigue life under superimposed sinusoidal wave ($f_1=1Hz, f_2=15Hz$).

Fig.9 Estimation of fatigue life under superimposed sinusoidal wave ($f_1=1Hz, f_2=20Hz$).

Fatigue life Prediction under Random Gaussian Stresses

The peak distribution of random process $X(t)$ normalized by the standard deviation S_X , ($Y(t)=X(t)/S_X$) is given by [3][4]

$$f_p(y) = \sqrt{\frac{1-\lambda^2}{2\pi}} \exp\left\{-\frac{y^2}{2(1-\lambda^2)}\right\} + \lambda y \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \Phi\left(\frac{\lambda y}{\sqrt{1-\lambda^2}}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$F_p(y) = \Phi\left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{1-\lambda^2}}\right) - \lambda \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \cdot \Phi\left(\frac{\lambda y}{\sqrt{1-\lambda^2}}\right) \quad (10)$$

Where $\Phi(\bullet)$ is a standard normal distribution function and λ is a irregularity ratio, representing the expected rate of upward zero crossings divided by the expected number of all peaks. In case of narrow band process of $\lambda=1$, the peak stress distribution approaches a Rayleigh distribution, giving such a function form that

$$f_p(y) = y \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \quad , \quad y \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

Whilst, the wide band process approaches a Gaussian(Normal) distribution represented by

$$f_p(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \quad , \quad -\infty < y < +\infty \quad (12)$$

It is well-known that the probability density function of the Weibull distribution has a wide variety of shapes. For instance, when $\alpha \cong 3.2$, the Weibull distribution is equivalent to the Normal distribution. The Rayleigh distribution is a Weibull distribution with $\alpha = 2$. For convenience, therefore, in this paper it seems reasonable to use such a two-parameter Weibull distribution, in approximation, for the peak distribution, providing

$$f_p(\sigma) = \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha-1} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right\} \quad (13)$$

$$F_p(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right\} \quad , \quad \sigma \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

Fig.10 Various random waves investigated.

(a) N-wave

(b) W-wave

(c) S-wave

Fig.11 Power spectral density and the histogram of peak stress.

Fig. 10 shows the random stress history of the three kinds of wave applied on the specimen. The so-called FFT analysis was performed as indicated in Fig. 11, in order to clarify the power spectral density of these random waves, indicating that the maximum power spectral of the Narrow-Band wave and the central frequency of the Wide-Band wave exist around the frequency of 10Hz. Hereinafter in the figure, let the Narrow-Band wave and the Wide-Band wave be called N-wave and W-wave respectively. The S-wave is such a superimposed wave that there exist two peaks of spectral density around 1 Hz and 2 Hz.

Fig.12 is the basic S-N diagram of the specimen under the sinusoidal wave of constant amplitude. The linear approximation between stress amplitude and expected fatigue life in log-log scale is drawn by a solid line and the exponential approximation by a dotted curve. And the equations were obtained by using a Least Square Error Method such as

$$\sigma^{12.2} \cdot N = 1.29 \times 10^{30} \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma^{1.28} \cdot \log N = 2.07 \times 10^3 \quad (16)$$

The discussions will now be given to the validity of evaluating the fatigue life under the random waves with the aid of equivalent stress amplitude whose damage concept is based upon Palmgren-Miner rule [5][6]. The equivalent stress is regarded as the constant stress amplitude corresponding to the same total number of repeated cycles to failure as that for the random load, and represented by

$$\sigma_{eq} = \left(\frac{\sum_i n_i \sigma_i^m}{\sum_i n_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (17)$$

Where m is the slope in linear approximation for S-N relationship. Using peak distribution of random wave, f_p , one obtains the following equation.

$$\sigma_{eq} = \left(\frac{\int_0^\infty \sigma^m f_p(\sigma) d\sigma}{\int_0^\infty f_p(\sigma) d\sigma} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (18)$$

Fig.12 S-N diagram for the constant amplitude fatigue.

Substitution of Eq.(13) into Eq.(18) provides

$$\sigma_{eq} = \beta \Gamma\left\{\left(\frac{m}{\alpha} + 1\right)\right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (19)$$

Since the two parameter Weibull distribution with $\alpha = 2$ gives a Rayleigh distribution which is the peak density function of narrow band process, thus

$$\sigma_{eq} = \beta \Gamma\left\{\left(\frac{m}{2} + 1\right)\right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (20)$$

It is clear therefore that the equivalent stress σ_{eq} can be determined from the Weibull parameter, α and β , and constant m of S-N relationship. Considering that the upper bound of the peak distribution f_p is practically limited to the maximum value of actually observed peak stress σ_{pmax} and therefore σ_{eq} is represented as

$$\sigma_{eq} = \left(\frac{\int_0^{\sigma_{pmax}} \sigma^m f_p(\sigma) d\sigma}{\int_0^{\sigma_{pmax}} f_p(\sigma) d\sigma} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (21)$$

On the other hand, assuming that S-N relationship is represented by Eq.(16) which seems to be better fitted expression than Eq.(15), one obtains

$$\sigma_{eq}^* = \left\{ \frac{C'}{\log \frac{\int_0^{\sigma_{pmax}} f_p(\sigma) d\sigma}{\int_0^{\sigma_{pmax}} f_p(\sigma) \cdot 10^{-\frac{C'}{\sigma^m}} d\sigma}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (23)$$

Fig.13 is the S-N diagram for the random waves, which represents the relationship between equivalent stress amplitude obtained by using Eq.(22) and fatigue life. The number of downward zero crossing was counted for evaluating the number of repeated cycles to failure under the random load spectra. In the figure, the solid line is the basic S-N relationship for the constant amplitude fatigue and the experimental data are given by circles. It is clear that the fatigue life of the GRP specimen under the random loads can satisfactorily be predicted with the aid of the equivalent stress representation.

Fig.13 Fatigue life prediction of GRP under the various random waves.

Concluding Remarks

Investigations were made on the fatigue life prediction of GRP subjected to the various loading patterns such as superimposed sinusoidal wave, narrow band wave, wide band wave, etc. Fatigue tests were conducted under the simulated random waves and then the procedure for predicting the fatigue life for those random waves was discussed. As a result, fatigue life prediction was favourable with the aid of the equivalent frequency as suggested in this paper. It was also shown that the fatigue life under the Gaussian random waves of narrow band and wide band could well be predicted by a modified equivalent stress method.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to acknowledge for the considerable assistance of Mr. A. Ochi, Matsushita Electric Industrial Co., Ltd.

References

- (1) T. Tanimoto and S. Amijima, "Fatigue life and its reliability of FRP under Multi-Step Loading", Proceedings of the Japan-U.S. Conference on Composite Material, pp.145-154 (1981).
- (2) S. Amijima, T. Tanimoto and T. Matsuoka, "A Study on the Fatigue Life Estimation of FRP under Random Loading", Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Composite Material pp.701-708 (1982).
- (3) P. H. Wirsching and E. B. Haugen, "A General Statistical Model for Random Fatigue", Transactions of the ASME, pp.34-40 (1974)
- (4) M. Shinozuka and J.-N. Yang, "Peak Structural Response to Non-Stationary Random Excitations", Journal of Sound and Vibration, Volume 16, pp.505-507, (1971)
- (5) A.Z. Palmgren, "Die Lebensdauer von Kugellagern", Z. Ver. Deutsch. Ing., Volume 68 pp.339 (1924).
- (6) M. A. Miner, "Cumulative Damage in Fatigue", Journal of Applied Mechanics, Volume 12, A159 (1945).